

**FRETTING FATIGUE OF CARBON
FIBRE REINFORCED LAMINATES**

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ABSTRACT

The fretting-fatigue properties of carbon fibre reinforced plastic (cfRP) laminates with stacking sequence of $[+45, 0, \pm 45, 90, \pm 45]_2$ and $[0, 90, 0, 90]_2$ were examined and compared to the equally executed plain fatigue tests. Varying three different pressures of fretting pads and pad materials (TiAl6V4, Al 7475 and a crfp-laminate with mainly 0° -plies) there had been 9 fretting variances. Apart from strongly differing behaviour of both laminates, it was shown that there is an essential influence of the fretting on the number of cycles until fracture. A reduction of the number of fatigue cycles due fretting up to three orders of magnitude was observed.

INTRODUCTION

The fatigue behaviour of carbon fibre reinforced laminates (cfRP) has been shown to be extremely good. Composite parts are therefore designed against static and not fatigue loading. However, in many engineering applications of crfp, a relative cyclic motion of two surfaces in intimate contact can become important because it constitutes the condition of a wear process known as fretting. The fretting fatigue situa-

tion occurs when repeated loading on a structural part causes this kind of oscillatory sliding movement at material interfaces in the design. This movement, in turn, must induce at or near points of contact between the faces stresses of sufficient intensity to cause surface damage. These fretting fatigue requirements are often encountered, and have often led to failure in an unpredictable manner, i.e. at flanges and bolted joints. Other design details that can give fretting fatigue problems are multilayer leaf springs, collars and bushes. In the past, most of these structural components have been made out of metallic materials. Therefore, it is not surprising that all of the scientific investigations concentrated on the problem of fretting fatigue were performed with metals. Many of the design examples mentioned above are now frequently made of polymer composites, consisting of a certain type of fibre reinforcement in a polymeric matrix. The reasons for using these materials are mainly weight reduction, cost efficiency, reduced stress corrosion problems, etc. The use of these materials often requires some changes in the design principles relative to those applied for manufacturing these components out of metallic materials. But even in spite of differences in the design, it cannot be neglected that similar fretting fatigue-load collectives may act on structural composite components as well. However, no fretting fatigue results on carbon fibre reinforced plastics have been reported in the literature up to now. Only a pilot study on the fretting fatigue characteristics of a glass fibre/polyester resin has been carried out by Friedrich [1]. It could be shown, that during fatigue an additional fretting component can reduce the fatigue life. The reduction in fatigue life was strongly dependent on the fibre arrangement. To prevent unexpected failure during fatigue life in a composite component, it is necessary to understand the fundamentals of fretting fatigue, which can lead to a designing of composite structural components which may encounter some kinds of fretting fatigue situations and to learn how to build up a composite structure, where fretting and fatigue

occurs simultaneously.

In the present study it is investigated in how far different carbon fibre arrangements in an epoxy matrix are sensitive to an additional fretting component, while the laminates are fatigued.

EXPERIMENTAL

For testing under fretting fatigue conditions a special loading device, shown in Fig. 1, was developed [2]. Two fretting pads (A) were pressed with a constant load, controlled by a separate load cell (B), from each side against a cfrp test coupon (C), while this was loaded in tension-tension fatigue with an R-value ($R = \sigma_{\min} / \sigma_{\max}$, σ_{\min} = minimum and σ_{\max} = maximum stress in each load cycle) of $R = 0,1$ and a frequency of 10 Hz.

The materials selected for investigation were two different crfp-laminates.

- Laminate A, a T 300-fibre (manufactured by Toray) and a resin 914 c (manufactured by Ciba-Geigy). The stacking sequence of Laminate A: $[\pm 45, 0, \pm 45, 90, \pm 45]_S$ resulted in a thickness of the laminate of about 6 mm.
- Laminate B, a HTA-fibre (manufactured by Toho-Beslon) and an Araldite LY556 (Bisphenol-A diglycide ether) resin, accelerator: HT976 (DDS= diamino diphenyl sulfon) both manufactured by Ciba-Geigy. The stacking sequence of laminate B: $[0_2, 90_2, 0_2, 90_2]_S$ resulted in a laminate thickness of 2 mm.

The laminates were available in the form of large sheets. Testpieces were cut out in lengths of about 200 mm with a cross section of approximately 6x6 mm for laminate A and 6x2 mm for laminate B (Fig. 1b).

The fretting pads were pressed with three different loads (150, 350, 450 N) against the front surface (laminate A.1 and B.1) and the edge surface (laminate A.2).

Three different pad materials were selected (TiAl6V4, Al 7475 and a crfp-laminate with 67 % 0^0 -plies). The crfp pads were pressed with the ends of the 0^0 -fibres against the laminates

investigated. The diameter of the fretting pads was 5 mm.

Fig. 1 a) Photo of the fretting fatigue tests device attached to a servohydraulic testing machine:
 A = fretting pads, B = load cell, C = sample
 D = fretting load device, E = upper and lower grips.

b) Specimen geometry of laminate B.

The fretting fatigue test device used, allowed different positions of the fretting pads along the gage length of the samples, thus different slip amplitudes Δl . However, in the present investigation no variation in the position of the fretting pads has been made.

RESULTS

Mechanical Properties

The static mechanical properties measured for the two laminates investigated are summarized in Table 1.

The mechanical properties are strongly dependent on the volume content of fibres in the 0° direction. In laminate A, only 8.33 % of the fibres are aligned in the loading direction, leading to a comparatively low fracture stress, σ_f . About 50 % of the fibres in laminate B, are positioned in the 0° direction, which results in a relatively high fracture stress. Also the elastic modulus; E , is mainly influenced by

the content of fibres in the 0^0 direction, while the strain to failure, ϵ_f , is dominated by the fibre properties. The latter is however, independent of the number of fibres in the 0^0 direction.

Table 1: Static mechanical properties of the laminates investigated

	Laminate A	Laminate B
Fracture Stress σ_f [MPa]	296	996
Elastic Modulus E [GPa]	27	77
Strain to Failure ϵ_f [%]	1,3	1,3

The mechanical properties of the fretting pads are summarized in Table 2. Additionally to the static properties also the Vickers-Hardness is included in the table. While the titanium has the highest Vickers-Hardness of the three pad materials the lowest was found for the crfp-pad.

Table 2: Mechanical properties of the fretting pads

	Al 7475	TiAl6V4	CFRP
σ_f [MPa]	450	990	920
E [GPa]	72	119	98
ϵ_f [%]	14	9,4	1,3
HV ₁₀ [MPa]	300	595	175

Fatigue Tests

Laminate A

Fretting fatigue tests with laminate A were performed on both the front surface (here the notation A.1 is used) and on the edge surface (notation A.2).

Fig. 2a.
Fretting fatigue results of
laminate A.1 at $F_N = 450$ N.

Fig. 2a summarizes the results on laminate A.1 with a contact pressure of the fretting pads of $F_N = 450$ N. The pure fatigue tests are marked by the full spots and the straight line. Only a slight deviation in fretting fatigue relative to the behaviour under pure fatigue was observed. Fretting - and this applies equally to TiAl6V4 or Al 7475 fretting pads - results in somewhat higher life. This was more marked at higher maximum loading in a fatigue cycle, σ_{max} , than at lower maximum loading. Using lower contact pressure, i.e. $F_N = 300$ N, or $F_N = 150$ N, gave the same results.

In Fig. 2b, the results of fretting fatigue against the edge surface of the specimen (laminate A.2) are plotted. Similar results to those of laminate A.1 were found. Again, the fretting fatigue values attain higher numbers of load cycles if σ_{max} is high and tend to be in the range of the pure fatigue test at low σ_{max} -values.

In addition no systematic influence could be found for the different pad materials.

Fig. 3 shows the results for laminate B.1 with fretting at $F_N = 450$ N against the front surface of the specimen. In this case the influence of fretting causes a great reduction in life when compared to the pure fatigue test. The highest reduction in fatigue life can be observed when using the TiAl6V4 pads, while with the Al 7475 pads a slightly less

Fig. 2b.
Fretting fatigue results of
laminate A.2 at $F_N = 450$ N.

Laminate B

Fig. 3. Fretting fatigue results of laminate B.1. at $F_N = 450$ N.

reduction in fatigue life is achieved. However, at higher σ_{\max} -values there is a remarked difference in fatigue life between the two pad materials. This difference is reduced at lower σ_{\max} -values. In the case of the cfrp-pad - in this instance only an investigation was carried out at $\sigma_{\max} = 700$ MPa - a pronounced reduction in fatigue life was observed, but the reduction was distinctly smaller as with the metal-pads.

The variation of the contact pressure also had a distinct influence to the number of cycles to failure. In Fig. 4, the results of three different pressure loads are plotted versus the number of cycles to failure for laminate B.1 at a maximum stress value of $\sigma_{\max} = 700$ MPa. The number of load cycles until failure for a test with no fretting is also included in the figure. It turns out, that the low pressure ($F_N = 150$ N) on the fretting pads only leads to a slight decrease in fatigue life. Increasing the pressure can cause a reduction in the number of fatigue cycles due to fretting up to three orders of magnitude. The material selected for the fretting pads, also has an effect on fatigue life, with the greatest effect being exerted by TiAl6V4 and the least by CFRP. Especially this latter effect can mainly be related to differences in the hardness of the various materials. While for the TiAl6V4-pads a hardness of $HV_{10} = 595$ MPa was measured, the Al 7475 pads had a hardness of $HV_{10} = 300$ MPa and the

CFRP-pads of $HV_{10} = 175$ MPa. It seems, that the higher the hardness of a pad-material the higher is its influence on the fatigue life reduction. But of course, this effect is exceeded by the influence of the pressure on the fretting pads.

Fig. 4: Variation of the number of load cycles to failure with normal contact load F_N on various fretting materials, for laminate B.1. at $\sigma_{max} = 700$ MPa.

Damage Analysis

Laminate A

Fig. 5a. Typical fracture pattern for laminate A.

Fig. 5b. Typical fracture pattern for laminate B.

It was shown for laminate A (compare Fig. 2a) that fretting fatigue does not lead to a reduction in fatigue life. On the contrary, a slight increase could be observed. Fig. 5a corroborates this result with respect to the failure of a sample of laminate A2. Failure did not occur at the fretting position, but between the lower grips and the pads. In fact, this result was repeatedly found in all the tests carried out with laminate A. An appropriate explanation can be given as follows:

1. In the case of laminate A.1, the fretting pads were pressed against the $\pm 45^\circ$ surface layers of the laminate. Damage induced was limited to the surface plies, which only carried a small amount of the load and protected the underlying load bearing 0° -plies.
2. In the region between the upper grip and the fretting pad a load F_I was acting, which was lower than the load F_{II} , acting on the specimen between the fretting pads and the lower grip. The actual difference was dependent on the frictional forces F_R , generated by the two fretting pads, via:

$$F_R = \mu \cdot F_N$$

where μ is the "effective coefficient of friction" between the fretting pads and the composite test sample. The frictional force was transferred into the upper grip through the fretting fatigue test device which was attached to it [2].

3. In the case of laminate A.2 only a small amount of 0° -fibres could be harmed by fretting against the side surface. The load transfer through the test device as described above superimposed this effect, so that failure could again occur between the fretting pads and the lower grips.

Laminate B

Fretting fatigue on laminate B.1 showed a reduction in fatigue life up to three orders of magnitude (Fig. 3 and 4). For this laminate, the fretting pads were pressed against the

surface layers of the test coupons which were the load bearing 0° -plies. The test samples always failed at the fretting pad position, independent of the pad material used (compare, Fig. 5b).

How was the damage, leading to failure of the sample, initiated? In Fig. 6, an X-radiograph of a test sample is shown that has exceeded about 80 % of its expected fatigue life. On the one hand a damage pattern typical for a crossply laminate under fatigue loading can be recognized: transverse and longitudinal interply cracks, edge delaminations, and interior delaminations at cross sections of longitudinal and transverse cracks [3]. In addition, at the center of the test sample, further damaged areas executed from the fretting pad can be recognized. In the surface 0° -layers numerous failure of the 0° -fibres occurred (see dart) and extensive delaminations between the 0° -plies and the underlying 90° -plies can be observed, often terminated by longitudinal cracks.

Fig. 6.

X-radiograph of laminate B.1 ($\sigma_{max} = 700\text{MPa}$, $F_N = 450\text{ N}$, Al 7475-pad). Sample has exceeded 80 % (4800 cycles) of its expected fatigue life.

Fig. 7. shows SEM-micrographs taken from the fretting area of a test sample of laminate B.1. The sample failed near the center of the fretting area, in which extensive damage can be recognized (Fig. 7a). The fretting pad particularly affected the 0° -fibres, since it was only pressed against the outer 0° -layer. This resulted in fibre abrasion (Fig. 7b). Debris of the fibres and matrix are distributed all over the fretting area, and fibres are partly abraded to half of their original thickness (Fig. 7c). At other locations, already broken 0° -fibres which have not yet been abraded, but have

been completely unseated by "fretting" can be observed (Fig. 7d).

CONCLUSION

Fretting fatigue can have a strong influence on the fatigue life of cfrp-samples, in the case when the fretting pads directly touch against load bearing 0^0 -plies. Then, the 0^0 -fibres are damaged by a fretting wear process, generated between the ply and the fretting pads during fatigue loading.

Fig. 7. SEM-micrographs of laminate B.1 ($\sigma_{\max} = 700$ MPa, $F_N = 450$ N, Al 7475-pad):

- a) Fretting fatigue fracture, overall view. b) Detail of fretted area taken from Fig. 7a.
 c) Abraded and broken 0^0 -fibres plus wear debris d) Broken 0^0 -fibres (detail of Fig. 7b).
 (detail of Fig. 7b).

High pressures on the fretting pads result in a tremendous reduction of the specimen's fatigue life. Also, different pad materials with a different hardness, can influence the fretting effect on the fatigue life, although this is not so critical as changes in the contact pressure (laminate B.1). If no or only very few 0^0 -fibres of a laminate are harmed during the fretting fatigue process, no significant life

reduction, compared to the "non-fretting" situation, can be found (laminate A.2). To be sure, that the influence of fretting fatigue diminishes, it seems suitable to protect the 0° -plies by $\pm 45^{\circ}$ -layers (laminate A.1).

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